

Direct gas heating in linear concentrating solar collectors for power and industrial process heat production: Applications and challenges

Antonio Lecuona-Neumann PhD

Departamento de Ingeniería Térmica y de Fluidos, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Correspondence

Antonio Lecuona-Neumann,
Departamento de Ingeniería Térmica y de Fluidos, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Avda. de la Universidad 30, 28911 Leganés, Madrid, Spain.
Email: lecuona.ing@uc3m.es

Funding information

Comunidad de Madrid (CAM), Grant/Award Number: IND2017/AMB7769; Funding for APC: Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (Agreement CRUE-Madroño 2023), Grant/Award Number: 2

Edited by: Manuel Romero, Associate Editor and Peter Lund, Co-Editor-in-Chief

Abstract

Parabolic trough collectors and linear Fresnel collectors are mature technologies for power production, and they are being recently applied to provide solar heat for industrial needs. Conventionally, they use a liquid as heat transfer fluid, either thermal oil or water, to carry heat from the receivers up to the point of conversion or delivery. Although liquids offer excellent thermal properties, they show technical limitations, besides environmental concerns, which have encouraged the research on alternative solutions. This work reviews the main research works on the use of gases as heat transfer fluid in linear concentrating collectors, including solar power and heat production, highlighting the potential applications and technical challenges. The review indicates: first, gases offer potential to replace liquids, and second, there is a need for more research and development to define the best technical compromises to reach practical application in every sector.

This article is categorized under:

Sustainable Energy > Solar Energy

Energy and Power Systems > Energy Infrastructure

KEYWORDS

hot air, solar collector, solar energy, solar gas heating, solar heat

1 | INTRODUCTION

In the past decades, Linear concentrating technologies such as parabolic trough collectors (PTCs) and linear Fresnel collector (LFC) have been developed for large-scale solar thermal plants aiming at electricity generation (Fuqiang et al., 2017) known as solar thermal electricity (STE).

The PTC is the most mature thermal concentrating solar power (CSP) technology (Bilal Awan et al., 2020; Fuqiang et al., 2017; Gharat et al., 2021, among others) including STE. As a basic common feature, in a PTC a cylindrical parabolic-shaped reflector focuses the incoming direct component of the solar irradiance. The tubular receiver is located on the focal line as in Figure 1a. The receiver is an evacuated tube with high thermal performance, usually made of a stainless-steel tube coated with a spectrally selective coating, embedded into a coaxial high solar transparency glass

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2023 The Authors. *WIREs Energy and Environment* published by Wiley Periodicals LLC.

FIGURE 1 Linear concentrating solar collectors. Parabolic trough collector (PTC) working principle (a). Linear Fresnel collector working principle (b) with an evacuated receiver and secondary reflector.

tube, evacuated in the annulus. A heat transfer fluid (HTF) with suitable thermal properties flows inside the receiver to evacuate heat and deliver it where required. A one-axis tracking system continuously adjusts the collector inclination and keeps the aperture as most perpendicular to the incident irradiance as possible with the tracking mechanism to reflect the direct solar radiation onto the receiver straight tube. As general rule for all applications, numerous parabolic troughs are connected in series forming a straight row. A loop is formed by one or more rows hydraulically connected in series to reach the desired temperature. A solar field consists of several loops, arranged in parallel to reach the desired power.

LFC technology has a little commercial share of CSP projects (Bellos, 2019), although a noticeable demonstration activity and research are ongoing. LFC is not a well-established technology (Zhu et al., 2014), which admits variations in the design and components (floorplan aperture, number and curvature of mirrors, types of receivers, secondary reflector, and tracking mechanism). An LFC has a segmented (primary) reflector obtained from a series of flat or slightly curved mirrors (Karathanasis, 2019). The tracking system adjusts the inclination of each mirror to simultaneously concentrate the incoming direct solar irradiance, usually on the receiver (Figure 1b). Because of the different distances of each reflector to the receiver, their curvature should be different if focusing on the same line. For focusing on the same line, the tracking angle of rotation is identical for all of them. Several types of receivers have been studied and applied, including single or multiple receivers, evacuated or nonevacuated. The most efficient receivers are the evacuated tubes (operation up to 500°C HTF outlet temperature), while the trapezoidal cavities are less expensive but less efficient (operation up to 300°C). In most applications, a secondary upside-down reflector is used for redirecting to the receiver the concentrated irradiance missing, due to imperfect focusing, either unavoidably or intentionally. Compared to PTCs, LFCs show some technical advantages, such as lower manufacturing costs, lower wind loads, simpler tracking systems, a lighter moveable part of the structure, and easy reflectors cleaning, all of them leading to lower costs (Bellos, 2019). The receiver is static, thus the connection of the receiver to the system has to only cope with the axial thermal dilatation, while PTCs require a moveable joint, either rotating or flexible. LFCs hold lower optical performances, especially for being the reflector horizontal (Abbas et al., 2016; Eck et al., 2014; Giostri et al., 2011; Morin et al., 2012). Only in equatorial latitudes, LFCs can approach the optical performance of PTCs. Blocking and shadowing between primary reflectors are also limiting (Karathanasis, 2019; Figure 2).

In CSP applications, the HTF is heated up to the desired temperature delivering the thermal power to the power block to currently drive a Rankine cycle for electricity production. In the most common layout, thermal oil circulates in the solar receiver as HTF, heating, in turn, a molten salt sensible thermal energy storage (TES), which drives the steam generation for the Rankine cycle (Figure 3).

Although they have been first developed for STE plants (Figure 2a,b), both PTC and LFC are recently considered suitable technologies for providing heat for industrial needs, besides specific developments, usually of smaller sizes. The solar field is not coupled anymore to a power block for energy conversion, since heat is the final output (Figure 4). Solar heat for industrial processes (SHIP) is a relatively new sector, which is growing all around the world.

FIGURE 2 Linear concentrating technologies. Example of thermal concentrating technologies at Plataforma Solar de Almeria (PSA, n.d.): (a) PTC (Eck et al., 2003); (b) LFC (Bernhard et al., 2008). Example for SHIP: PTC (c) by Inventive Power (n.d.) and LFC (d) by Solatom (n.d.). LFC, linear Fresnel collector; PTC, parabolic trough collector; SHIP, solar heat for industrial processes.

FIGURE 3 Simplified basic diagram of conventional STE plant using thermal oil as HTF. The solar field is simplified to a single loop of PTCs or LFCs. Molten salt-based thermal energy storage (TES) can be present (dashed lines). HTF, heat transfer fluids; LFCs, linear Fresnel collectors; PTCs, parabolic trough collectors; STE, solar thermal electricity.

According to International Energy Agency (2018), heat takes a large share of energy consumption in the industrial sector. Solar energy has a great potential for replacing fossil fuel consumption for heat production in industry, aiming at greenhouse gases and pollutant emission reduction, nonforgetting environmental sustainability (Farjana et al., 2018;

FIGURE 4 Linear concentrating collector layout for industrial process heat (SHIP). The solar field is simplified as a single loop with PTCs or LFCs. Thermal Energy Storage TES can be present (dashed lines). LFCs, linear Fresnel collectors; PTCs, parabolic trough collectors; SHIP, solar heat for industrial processes.

Mekhilef et al., 2011; A. K. Sharma et al., 2017). Among solar thermal technologies, linear concentrating collectors, either PTC or LFC, are the suitable solution in the low-to-medium temperature range, below 400°C, corresponding to around half of the total heat consumption in the industry (International Renewable Energy Agency, n.d.). Due to their modularity, they can be adapted to small- and medium-scale facilities suitable for installation in industries. Both LFCs and PTCs optimized for SHIP application are commercially available (Figure 2c,d). The SHIP database (SHIP Database) 2022 reports 60 projects using PTCs with solar field areas ranging from 34 to 5060 m². From the same source, 21 existing plants use LFCs for SHIP from 123 m² of aperture surface up to 2000 m².

Regarding the mismatch of the heat demand in front of the solar production time profile, there are three possibilities: (1) implementing heat storage (TES), (2) using a backup source while solar production cover only a portion (solar fraction) of the overall consumption, and (3) a combination of (1) and (2) (Figure 4). This figure does not show any backup source as they are diverse and can be implemented in series or in parallel either in the supply circuit or in the consumption apparatus of the thermal process.

Current practice for HTF is oriented to liquid substances with suitable thermal properties, mainly thermal oil for STE applications and pressurized water predominating in SHIP projects, where internal evaporation is avoided. The use of gases as an HTF seems to offer some potential for application both in STE and SHIP due to their lower environmental impact, cost, and leakage risks, among other technical advantages, but some technical challenges are still unsolved, and experience is short.

Throughout the following sections, this work reviews the main research and development carried out and highlights the main advantages and limitations of several gaseous HTFs in comparison with the widespread liquid alternatives. It focuses on emerging SHIP applications and challenges.

2 | APPLICATIONS

Although sharing the same principles, both PTC and LFC technologies differ when applied to STE or SHIP, in several terms. Such are a smaller scale of the solar field, collector sizes and concentration ratio, differences in components, and operating conditions (temperature, flow rate). The HTF requirements also change according to the specific applications. The present section reviews the main trends and research work on alternative gaseous HTFs either for STE or SHIP.

2.1 | Solar thermal electricity

With STE, the large-scale applications dominate, which goes together with large apertures and concentration ratios. Thermal oils, such as Dowtherm™ A and Therminol™ VP-1, are the most common choices as HTF due to their good

thermal properties (Zarza, 2016). Their main drawbacks are related to labor safety and environmental concerns in case of leaks from the solar plant circuit, besides the associated fire hazard. From the thermodynamics point of view, the HTF's limited working temperature ($\lesssim 400^\circ\text{C}$) curtails the maximum power Rankine cycle temperature and consequently the conversion efficiency of the plant (Figure 3). Oil also degrades during the operation. For around 4% of the total oil must be replaced and disposed of every year (Giglio et al., 2017). Crystallization at low ambient temperatures represents an issue affecting operating strategies and increasing O&M (OPEX) concerns and costs.

Among the alternative HTFs, nitrate molten salts have received considerable attention in replacing thermal oil in CSP applications especially with PTC, although commercial applications are still a few. Their main advantage is the higher operating temperature, above 500°C , enabling a higher conversion efficiency, but the high solidification temperature, $\sim 220^\circ\text{C}$, requires a dedicated heating system to avoid plant damage, increasing the complexity, costs, and maintenance operations (Zarza, 2016).

In general terms, gases can operate at much higher temperatures without any degradation, and most of them do not present risks because of leakages. Under this framework, research on gaseous HTFs has been encouraged (Benoit et al., 2016). According to Zarza (2016), the larger temperature difference across the solar field reduces the volume of the heat storage needed (Figure 3). Air, nitrogen (N_2), and carbon dioxide (CO_2) have received most of the attention. Steam is considered an HTF in the framework of direct steam generation (DSG), where the water is preheated and evaporated in a once-through process taking place inside the receiver tubes, to obtain either saturated or even superheated steam. The direct use of single-phase steam as a gaseous HTF has not received attention.

One of the most relevant research projects on gaseous HTF with PTCs has been carried out at Plataforma Solar de Almeria (PSA; Muñoz-Anton et al., 2014; PSA, n.d.). CO_2 was preferred among other gases as HTF in an experimental test facility made of two 50-m length ET-II PTC collectors with an aperture of 5.76 m, operating in a closed circuit, pressurized up to 100 bar and at 525°C of maximum temperature.

Biencinto et al. (2014) presented a new concept for solar thermal power plants through a theoretical investigation on a PTC-based STE using pressurized N_2 as HTF. Therefore, the solar field is configured by parallel subfields using ET-II collectors. Molten salt is used as secondary HTF carrying heat from the subfields to the power block, as represented in Figure 5. Biencinto et al. (2019) presents a similar concept applied to supercritical CO_2 as HTF inside large aperture PTCs, equipped with an evacuated receiver with a larger inner diameter than the commercial standard of 70 mm (Rioglass, n.d.) so that pressure loss is diminished and capturing concentrated rays is easier.

Bellos et al. (2016) compared various liquid and gaseous HTFs for their usage inside a PTC. Air, N_2 , CO_2 , He, and argon (Ar) were analyzed to determine the best working conditions for each gas. In a further study, the PTC technology operating with gas using longitudinal internal fins was studied by (Bellos, Tzivanidis, Daniil, et al., 2017). Bellos, Tzivanidis, and Antonopoulos (2017a) evaluated the energy and exergy performances of pressurized air, CO_2 , and He, compared with liquid HTFs in PTCs. Supercritical CO_2 was theoretically explored by Bellos and Tzivanidis (2017).

Air in large PTCs was investigated using nonconventional concentrating technology, based on very large PTCs with original cavity receivers. Good et al. (2015) proposed an original cavity receiver for operating with air temperatures

FIGURE 5 Simplified diagram of a STE plant using pressurized gases as HTF, following Biencinto et al. (2014) and Biencinto et al. (2019). The solar field is simplified as a single loop of PTCs. HTF, HTF, heat transfer fluid; PTCs, parabolic trough collectors; STE, solar thermal electricity.

above 600°C. Bader et al. (2015) also developed an innovative cavity receiver for usage with a large-span PTC using a 9 m of aperture heating air up to 500°C.

Pressurized air heated inside PTCs has been considered for integration with Brayton cycles for power production. To reach competitive efficiency, this cycle needs high air temperature, in the range of 600–1000°C and up. Linear concentrating collectors, with the current technology, do not allow these temperatures, but they can be still used as air preheaters for a combustion chamber (cc) to power a Brayton cycle as a solar-assisted gas turbine, either as a simple cycle or as a Rankine combined cycle (Ahmadi et al., 2018; Figure 6). Air can either be directly preheated by flowing inside the solar collectors or indirectly through a heat exchanger (HX; Behar, 2018). Amelio et al. (2014) studied an open solar-assisted combined Brayton cycle using PTCs, heating compressed air into a PTC solar field up to 580°C before entering the combustion chamber. One similar example of a solar-assisted gas turbine is studied by Bellos, Tzivanidis, and Antonopoulos (2017b). The pressure ratio is limited by inlet air temperature at the solar field (outlet compressor air temperature) unless intercooled compression is implemented (Dabwan et al., 2022). The use of a linear concentrating collector as the unique heat source in the power cycle has been studied to less extent, aiming at lower maximum temperature and modest efficiency, considering the Brayton cycle (Ferraro & Marinelli, 2012), or a discrete steps Ericsson cycle (Cinocca et al., 2018).

DSG represents an important field of research that up to now has involved both the PTC (Eck et al., 2003; Zarza et al., 2006) and LFC (Bernhard et al., 2008; Montes et al., 2014, among others). The HTF in the solar field is replaced

FIGURE 6 Simplified diagram of direct air heating in linear concentrating collectors with a Brayton cycle configuration. The solar field is simplified to a single loop of PTCs or LFCs. A combustion chamber (cc) can be present (dashed lines). LFCs, linear Fresnel collectors; PTCs, parabolic trough collectors.

FIGURE 7 Simplified diagram of direct steam generation DSG for STE. The solar field is simplified to a single loop of PTCs or LFCs. A recirculation circuit and separator (dashed line) can be used. DSG, direct steam generation; LFCs, linear Fresnel collectors; PTCs, parabolic trough collectors; STE, solar thermal electricity.

by water which is preheated, evaporated, and converted into saturated or superheated steam inside the receivers (Figure 7). A power block steam generator and an HTF/steam HX are not required anymore, achieving layout simplification and potentially lower installation costs. The solar field is directly coupled with the power block in an STE layout. Zarza (2016) summarizes the research effort carried out on DSG development. DSG has reached commercial application for both technologies, although LFC counts with a greater number of plants than PTC. Minor attention has been given to direct vapor generation in organic Rankine cycles, systems, worth mentioning (Loni et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2015).

Despite the published relevant numerical works as well as important experimental research projects on gases heated inside PTC, there is a lack of commercial examples of STE. Concerning LFC, it has been considered a technology for DSG (Bellos, 2019). Their use with pressurized gases as HTF has been rarely studied, as in one numerical study by Montes et al. (2016), where air at 90 bar is considered as HTF, besides water/steam, for comparison with PTC under similar conditions.

2.2 | Solar heat for industrial processes

Regarding SHIP, the trends differ from STE. The typical scale is much lower than in conventional STE, so shorter rows and loops are commonly used for smaller fields. Concentrating technologies go toward lower concentration ratios, aiming at lower procurement and maintenance costs, and less skyline invasion because of a smaller aperture. This is especially noticeable for PTCs, which even exhibit so small apertures as 1 m and nonevacuated small diameter receivers in most of the existing applications. LFCs, thanks to their lower cost, low suspended weight, and small frontal area, are viable with larger apertures. The higher concentration ratios overcome their lower optical efficiency. Lower temperatures than STE ($<250^{\circ}\text{C}$) are common practice in SHIP applications so increasing the operating temperature has limited relevance.

Water is used as HTF in most of the SHIP installations using PTCs. It offers excellent thermophysical properties but presents the main issue of low boiling point, not forgetting the need for pure water. For applications above 100°C , pressurization is needed to maintain the liquid state. The higher the operating temperature, the higher the pressure required and hence the technical requirements and leakage risk, with associated costs and safety issues. Easily affordable 15–20 bar is enough for an operating temperature of 200°C , but very high pressure is required for increased operating temperatures (85 bar @ 300°C , 165 bar @ 350°C). Indeed, SHIP applications using water do not exceed $200\text{--}250^{\circ}\text{C}$. Technical issues concerning water usage are the corrosion problem affecting the carbon steel components, in addition to the freezing problem, arising during nonoperating cold hours with ambient temperature below 0°C . Water/glycol mixtures have been used in a few SHIP plants to lower the freezing point, incorporating the need of replacing the anti-freeze agent for its potential corrosion action. Alternatively, a drain-back operation is required to empty the outdoor water circuit during cold hours. This is complex for the largest SHIP plants. In addition to that, pretreating equipment is required to demineralize fresh water before injecting it into the circuit, for start-up and makeup water.

The large use of steam in industry and the associated technological maturity motivated the efforts toward DSG. In existing applications, saturated steam seems a more attractive option than superheated steam due to its easy integration into the user steam grid. A review of existing installations (SHIP Database, n.d.) showed that the use of PTC as direct solar thermal steam boiler systems is less common than LFC. A few additional works cover the topic. Holler et al. (2021) exposed a feasibility study of superheated steam production in the beverage industry. Superheated steam was provided at $160\text{--}180^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a pressure of 8 bar in the solar field, considering two aperture areas of 3360 and 4480 m^2 . Cundapí et al. (2017) performed a study on the absorber tube for the direct steam generation with small aperture PTCs for industrial applications. They considered a module aperture of 1 m, length of 2 m, an absorber diameter external/internal 18/15 mm, with 76 m of loop length. LFCs seem more suitable for steam generation than PTCs, according to Sepúlveda et al. (2019). Haagen et al. (2015) reported an applied example where a saturated steam generation plant for industry using LFC is described. Eighteen LFC modules are installed on the rooftop of the factory in two rows with a total aperture area of 396 m^2 . Water is partially evaporated in the receivers. Steam at 6 bar, 166°C is separated from water in the external steam drum, while water is recirculated back to the solar field. To maintain a constant mass inside the system, softened water is pumped into the bottom of the steam drum while steam is withdrawn. Hongn and Flores Larsen (2018) offered a study of the hydrothermal behavior of DSG in a small LFC facility for industry, using saturated and superheated steam for a multitube trapezoidal receiver. The model was validated against experimental data of a prototype installed in San Carlos, Argentina.

The use of pressurized gases such as CO₂ or N₂ for HTF in SHIP applications, although they received some interest for STE, has not been studied, according to the open literature. On the other hand, air heating in PTCs and LFCs has recently received moderate interest. Together with steam, air is one of the most used fluids in industrial processes (Farjana et al., 2018; A. K. Sharma et al., 2017), for thermal processing of materials, manufactured products, biomass, and water treatments, drying, curing, and cooking. Depending on the application, the air temperature requirements vary from the low-temperature range (<150°C) up to medium temperatures and high temperatures (>400°C). Solar air heating up to medium temperature can be achieved by using linear concentrating collectors either indirectly, using a primary liquid HTF in the solar field, or even directly, using air as HTF inside the receivers. A few examples of indirect heating up to 160–180°C are reported in the technical literature using LFCs (Pietruschka et al., 2016; Rehman et al., 2019; SHIP Database, n.d.) or using PTCs (SHIP Database, n.d.). In these works, the layout is using water or thermal oil as HTF and an HTF/air HX upstream of the industrial thermal processes.

Nowadays, direct solar air heating is widely experimented with by using flat plate air collectors below 150°C (Saxena et al., 2015). Recent works focus on the use of ambient air as HTF in concentrating collectors for SHIP applications near ambient pressure in an open to atmosphere circuit (OAC) layout up to medium temperatures (300–400°C) primarily aiming at layout simplification and lower costs. As for a nonconcentrating solar air heater, the OAC could be implemented for industrial solar hot air generation, avoiding the need for a primary HTF as well as an HTF/air HX, with the advantage of a higher delivery temperature, achievable thanks to the corresponding higher thermal efficiency of linear concentrating collectors.

Xuening et al. (2015) offer an original numerical study using PTCs delivering air at 280°C at 2 bar. Hot pressurized air is used to evaporate brine from a desalination process in a spray evaporation tower. Kasperski and Nemš (2013) proposed a concentrating solar air heater, which uses PTCs for direct air heating. They analyzed different types of internal longitudinal fins for enhancing the receiver-to-flow heat transfer and evaluated the thermohydraulic collector efficiency, which includes pumping power consumption. Famiglietti et al. (2020) offered a comprehensive theoretical analysis of a concentrating solar air heater (SAH). The high pumping power arises as a practical constraint to the design of the solar field, limiting to short rows and moderate apertures. In the main conclusion, they stated that direct atmospheric air heating with PTC/LFC is energetically feasible within a restricted range of design parameters. In the same study, the authors introduced the innovative concept of Turbo-assisted concentrating solar air heater (T-SAH; Lecuona-Neumann, 2016; Figure 8). The original layout uses an automotive turbocharger coupled with the solar field operating with air. This minimizes the pressure drops and avoids the external auxiliary pumping power consumption, while an auxiliary electrical compressor only is needed for starting.

A further study (Famiglietti et al., 2021) presented a feasibility study of T-SAH on an industrial scale. Commercial LFCs and large-size automotive turbochargers were considered for the scope. A first small-scale experimental prototype of the T-SAH was designed and installed in Madrid, Spain (Famiglietti & Lecuona, 2021a). The results corroborate the practical viability of the concept and indicated relevant features and critical aspects for scaling up to industrial size. Further work (Famiglietti & Lecuona, 2021b) details the experimental investigation performed on the T-SAH prototypes

FIGURE 8 Open to atmosphere circuit concentrating solar air heater for industrial processes according to Famiglietti et al. (2020). The solar field is simplified as a single loop of PTCs or LFCs. Turbine *e*, compressor *c*, auxiliary electrical compressor *ac*. A turbocharger can be used for pumping (turbo-assisted SAH), otherwise only the electrical compressor *ac* is active.

TABLE 1 Main thermal properties of gaseous and liquid heat transfer fluids (HTFs).

	Temp. (°C)	Pressure (bar)	Density (kg m ⁻³)	Thermal conductivity (W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Dynamic viscosity (μPa s)	Kinematic viscosity (mm ² s ⁻¹)	Specific heat (kJ kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Carbon dioxide	400	1–100	0.78–78.83	0.047–0.05	30.7–31.4	39.06–0.399	1.11–1.17
Nitrogen	400	1–100	0.5–47.96	0.049–0.05	31.9–32.5	63.92–0.678	1.09–1.11
Air	400	1–100	0.5–49.79	0.05–0.052	33.3–34.1	64.35–0.684	1.07–1.09
Helium	400	1–100	0.071–7.02	0.274–0.278	34.9–35.0	652–4.98	5.19–5.18
Superheated Steam	400	1–100	0.32–37.82	0.055–0.069	24.4–24.5	75–0.649	2.07–3.09
<i>Water (liq.)</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>997</i>	<i>0.607</i>	<i>890</i>	<i>0.89</i>	<i>4.18</i>
<i>Water (liq.)</i>	<i>300</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>715</i>	<i>0.55</i>	<i>86.4</i>	<i>0.12</i>	<i>5.68</i>
<i>Thermal oil</i>	<i>400</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>694</i>	<i>0.075</i>	<i>201</i>	<i>0.29</i>	<i>2.6</i>

Note: Italics designate liquid HTFs.

focusing on the air heating and receiver behavior. High temperatures are reached under continuous operation, up to 500°C for the air at the receiver outlet, and close to 600°C for the tube wall without damage. One exceptional quality of this innovation is the self-adjusting outlet temperature when solar input varies.

3 | CHALLENGES

Gases of interest as HTFs such as CO₂, air, N₂, steam, and He, offer thermophysical properties which differ from the common liquid HTFs (Benoit et al., 2016). Compared to a liquid substance, they offer lower specific heat capacity c_p , lower density ρ and thermal conductivity k , and higher viscosity μ . Besides, they vary among them Table 1. At the same pressure and temperature, CO₂ has the highest density, which is favorable. He has higher thermal conductivity and specific heat, favorable too. Air, very similar to nitrogen, shares the highest viscosity with He, and it is the only one that can be used in an OAC, carrying a substantial layout simplicity.

Among the gases considered for HTFs, CO₂ represents a superior behavior due to its higher density, as indicated by Muñoz-Anton et al. (2014). As the main drawback, it is incompatible with graphite sealing above 400°C (Zarza, 2016). In case of water presence, CO₂ could react to form carbonic acid (H₂CO₃), which is corrosive to carbon steel. CO₂ shows even better properties when working under supercritical conditions, above its critical point (30.98°C, 73.77 bar). For its good thermal properties, it has been considered the coolant in nuclear power plants, and also proposed in Rankine and Brayton cycles as a working fluid (W. L. Cheng et al., 2017; Crespi et al., 2020; Ma & Turchi, 2011; Sarkar, 2015, among others). N₂ poses a less corrosion issue than air or CO₂, and it can be obtained on-site from the air. He presents the risk of leakage due to its small atoms.

Thermophysical properties concur to determine the thermo-hydraulic behavior of the gases, which is the most challenging aspect of their design and operation. This issue is considered by most of the studies reviewed and mainly supported by theoretical and numerical analysis, but just in a few cases supported by experiments. The inclusion of O₂, H₂, CO, CH₄, and other gases for the innovative techniques, thermal solar fuel synthesis at high temperatures (Z. D. Cheng et al., 2019; Warren & Weimer, 2022) or photosolar water splitting for green H₂ (Salcedo-Abraira et al., 2021), seems of high interest. Whether linear concentrating solar collectors would play a role in those technologies has still to be determined.

3.1 | Basic equations

To clarify the relationship between the different design and operating parameters on the performance of the technology and their dependence on HTF properties, simple 1D steady-state models, considering constant fluid-thermal properties, are much highlighting and accurate, owing to the slenderness of the receiving tubes. Linear concentrating collectors, either of the PTC or LFC types, reflect the direct component of solar irradiance G_{bn} impacting on the primary reflector

area $A_a = W_a L$ toward the receiver tube with a certain optical efficiency η_{op} . The heat flux \dot{q}_s on a tubular receiver external surface $A_r = LP_{ex}$ can be expressed as in Equation (1).

$$\dot{q}_s = \frac{G_{bn}\eta_{op}A_a}{A_r} = \frac{G_{bn}\eta_{op}W_a}{P_{ex}} = G_{bn}\eta_{op}C, \quad (1)$$

$P_{ex} = D_{ex}\pi$ is the external perimeter of the receiver tube with an external diameter D_{ex} . The concentration ratio $C \equiv W_a/P_{ex}$ is a relevant parameter for the collector characterization.

The collectors' row length L can be adjusted to any desired value, arranging in series several collector modules in a row. In STE installations, very long rows $L \sim 100$ to 1000 m are the standard practice, owing to the high thermal capacity of liquids. Smaller $L \sim 10$ to 100 m are typically considered for SHIP applications. The primary reflector aperture W_a varies according to the collector model, from ~ 1 m for small size PTC (SHIP), up to ~ 8 m for the largest examples in CSP. For Linear Fresnel collectors, W_a is the sum of the aperture w_m of n_m mirrors constituting the discretized primary reflector, typically $W_a = w_m n_m \sim 5$ m in SHIP, up to $W_a \sim 20$ m for CSP. Concentration ratios are above $C \sim 25$ for PTC in CSP, while limited to $C \lesssim 20$ for SHIP. LFCs for CSP exhibit up to $C \sim 50$ or $C \sim 20$ for SHIP. The maximum optical efficiency range between $\eta_{op,max} \sim 0.5$ to 0.8 from low-end LFCs to high-end PTCs. The off-design figures are lower due to the cosine effect, and optical end losses, among other effects, according to the solar incidence angle, summing up both lateral and axial components through an incidence angle modifier IAM.

HTF temperature T and wall temperature T_w increase downstream of the row, making the last receiver tubes critical. Wall temperature is higher in the direction of the impacting rays, but turbulent inner convection helps in homogenization besides wall heat conduction. Assuming a radially averaged tube wall temperature and \dot{q}_s , the thermal balance equation on the receiver cross-section, Equation (2) shows that part of the incoming heat flux \dot{q}_s is lost to the ambient as losses \dot{q}_L . The resulting heat flux to the HTF \dot{q}_u is controlled by the heat loss transfer coefficient h across the internal circular perimeter $P = D\pi\varphi$. This is indicated in Equation (2) as the metallic wall of the tube is a much lower thermal resistance from the surface absorption to the HTF. The factor $\varphi \geq 1$ accounts for extended surfaces (internally finned tube). It is $\varphi = 1$ for smooth tubes, which is the common case.

$$\dot{q}_u = \dot{q}_s - \underbrace{U_L(T_w - T_{amb})}_{\dot{q}_L} = \frac{hP(T_w - T)}{P_{ex}}. \quad (2)$$

The thermal losses coefficient U_L is a wall temperature-dependent coefficient resulting from the heat transfer mechanisms involved toward ambient, according to the receiver configuration and material properties. Under nominal operation, an indicative value can be $3 - 5 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Duffie et al., 1985) for evacuated tubes. They offer relatively low U_L since the vacuum in the annulus minimizes the convection losses, the selective coating reduces the reradiation losses and self-radiation (Burkholder & Kutscher, 2009; Forristall, 2003) while the external glass cover tube can be IR opaque and include antireflective coatings. Other configurations, such as nonevacuated tubes, noncovered tubes, and glazed cavity receivers, offer higher U_L .

The Dittus–Boelter correlation (Incropera & DeWitt, 1996) gives a first approximation of the turbulent wall-to-flow internal heat transfer h (Equation 3), which depends on the flow Reynolds and Prandtl numbers (Equation 4), being $D_h = D\varphi$ the circular hydraulic diameter, and \dot{m} is the mass flow rate.

$$h = \frac{k}{D_h} 0.023 \text{Re}_{D_h}^{0.8} \text{Pr}^{0.4}, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Re}_{D_h} = \frac{4\dot{m}}{\mu\pi D\varphi} \gtrsim 5000; \text{Pr} = \frac{\mu c_p}{k} \sim 0.7. \quad (4)$$

Equation (3) shows that low thermal conductivity, typical of gaseous HTF excepting He, Table 1, limits h , although thermal oil shows a value in between. As a consequence, the wall over-temperature ΔT_w normally almost negligible with liquid HTFs becomes relevant and can turn into a design or operating constraint for the material of the most downstream tubes. As shown in Equation (5), ΔT_w is higher as higher the heat flux \dot{q}_s is; hence its effect grows with collector aperture, ceteris paribus. This equation also indicates the effect of density and velocity.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta T_w &= T_w - T = \frac{\dot{q}_u P_{\text{ex}}}{h P} \\ \dot{m} &= \frac{\rho v \pi D^2}{4} \\ \text{Equations (3) and (4)} \end{aligned} \right\} \Delta T_w \propto \approx \frac{\dot{q}_s}{\underbrace{\left(\frac{\dot{m}^{0.8}}{D^{1.8}}\right)}_{\approx (\rho v)^{0.8}}} \varphi^{1.2}. \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, the Reynolds number of the flow plays an important role in determining h and subsequently ΔT_w . For a given fluid, Re_{D_h} is related to the mass flow rate flowing into the receiver \dot{m} in Equation (4), which is imposed by the thermal balance of the collector row as in Equation (6). Once the extreme temperatures are defined by the application, \dot{m} is determined by the collector aperture W_a according to the row length L , determining the total solar heat power delivered to the flow \dot{Q}_u .

$$\dot{Q}_u = P \int_0^L \dot{q}_u dx = \dot{m}(i_{\text{out}} - i_{\text{int}}) = \dot{m} c_p (T_{\text{ou,t}} - T_{\text{in,t}}). \quad (6)$$

For a given fluid, a low \dot{m} translates into a low Re_{D_h} , thus a low h (Equations 3 and 4). The thermal balance equation on a generic cross-section of the receiver shows as the lower h the higher the wall overtemperature ΔT_w is (Equation 5), which leads to higher T_w for a given T . Since the thermal losses increase with T_w , a low h leads to higher thermal losses, reducing the thermal efficiency of the collector η_t (Equation 7).

$$\eta_t = \frac{\dot{Q}_u}{\dot{Q}_s} = \frac{P \int_0^L \dot{q}_u dx}{P_{\text{ex}} \int_0^L \dot{q}_s dx}. \quad (7)$$

Besides, when ΔT_w is not negligible, the maximum thermal limit of the receiver tube can be reached even if the fluid temperature is not critical by itself, limiting the maximum fluid temperature achievable to $T_{\text{max}} = T_{w,\text{max}} - \Delta T_w$. The maximum allowable temperature $T_{w,\text{max}}$ of the receiver tube is indicated by the manufacturer, with the main goal of preventing selective coating degradation. $T_{w,\text{max}}$ varies from 450 to 600°C with current technology. When T_{max} is defined by the application and $T_{w,\text{max}}$ by the receiver technology, the allowable ΔT_w turns into a constraint on other design parameters such as W_a or L . (Famiglietti et al., 2020) found a minimum L allowable by this thermal limit for direct air heating with PTC and LFC, being short rows associated with both low \dot{m} and h . (Famiglietti & Lecuona, 2021b) experimentally observed a decrease in thermal efficiency due to high ΔT_w (up to $\sim 200^\circ\text{C}$) in a small scale LFC with air as HTF.

3.2 | Hydraulic issues

As indicated above, increasing \dot{m} is beneficial for the internal heat rate removal from the wall but affects the stagnation t pressure drop along the receiver tube and external tubing $\Delta p_t = p_{\text{in,t}} - p_{\text{ou,t}}$. Equation (8) shows both its kinetic and frictional components, respectively $\Delta p_{k,t}$ and $\Delta p_{f,t}$ while K_n considers localized pressure losses (bends, connections, and cross-section variations). The average m Darcy friction factor f and ρ characterize the distributed losses on the internal tube, considered as the smallest D_h of the loop. They can be estimated using the Blasius correlation for smooth tubes (Equation 9) for a low Mach number but dilatating flow.

$$\Delta p_t = \overbrace{\frac{1}{2}(\rho_{\text{ou}} v_{\text{ou}}^2 - \rho_{\text{in}} v_{\text{in}}^2)}^{\Delta p_{k,t}} + \overbrace{\frac{1}{2} \rho_m v^2 \left(f \frac{L\varphi + L_c}{D} + K_n \right)}^{\Delta p_{f,t}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{4\dot{m}}{\pi D^2} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{\rho_{\text{ou}}} - \frac{1}{\rho_{\text{in}}} + f \frac{L\varphi + L_c}{\rho_m D} + \frac{K_n}{\rho_m} \right), \quad (8)$$

$$f = 0.316 \operatorname{Re}_{D_h}^{-\frac{1}{4}} \text{ for } 3,000 \lesssim \operatorname{Re}_{D_h} \lesssim 20,000. \quad (9)$$

It is worth mentioning that the overall circuit length can be larger than just the collector row length L , as connection tubes are needed, L_c in Equation (8), connecting more rows at their ends to configure the loop. Besides when scaling up to a large solar field made of several subfields, a nonnegligible pipe length is needed to connect the loops with the fluid delivery point.

The pumping power required to move the HTF across the collector row can be evaluated by considering a pumping compressor isentropic efficiency, total to total, η_{ptt} (Equation 10) with average properties p . For the compressible flow, the pumping power is expressed as in Equation (11), which considers a perfect gas.

$$\dot{W}_p = \frac{\dot{m} \Delta p_t}{\eta_{\text{ptt}} \rho_p} \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{W}_p = \dot{m} \frac{c_{p,p} T_{p,\text{in}}}{\eta_{\text{ptt}}} \left[\left(1 + \frac{\Delta p_t}{p_{p,\text{in}}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_p - 1}{\gamma_p}} - 1 \right]; \gamma_p = \frac{c_{p,p}}{c_{v,p}} \quad (11)$$

For a given receiver internal diameter D , the higher \dot{m} , the higher the flow mean velocity v is, which mainly increases Δp_t . The lower ρ , the higher v , as well as Δp_t (Equation 8). It follows that Δp_t is always a constraint when dealing with gaseous HTF, having much lower densities than liquids. Moreover, there is a relation between \dot{m} and L , which is controlled by imposing the desired temperature increment across the row and C (Equation 1). A long row with a large collector aperture requires a high \dot{m} (as higher as lower the c_p is) to absorb the incoming thermal power and limit the row wall outlet temperature (Equation 6). The pumping power (Equations 10 and 11) can be the limiting constraint on the collector row length and aperture, much more limiting using gases than liquid HTFs.

In CSP with a gaseous HTF, as large-scale plants are the standard, the pumping power will be a limiting constraint due to the long rows as well as the large aperture of the typical collectors (PTC and LFC).

High pressure is unavoidable for reducing the pressure drops down to reasonable values. The consulted literature is also clear about gas pressurization as an efficient way to reduce the pressure drops and the pumping power in a collector row. The pressure drop reduction is related to pressure by a quadratic relation (Equation 8; 10 times pressure increase means 100 times Δp_t). As a drawback, high pressurization poses problems in the joints and flanges, especially for moving elements such as ball joints in PTC plants so that robust designs must be used, and safety issues considered.

As for comparison, a typical STE plant loop of PTCs ($W_a = 5.7$ m) is of $L \sim 570$ m, operating with $\dot{m} \sim 5$ kg s⁻¹ of thermal oil (Figure 3). An optimized equivalent DSG LFC loop is typically longer, $L \sim 860$ to 1,140 m, operating with $\dot{m} \sim 2$ kg s⁻¹ of water (Figure 7). Due to the high-pressure drop of the steam section, working pressures below 50 bar are not recommended. Pressure of 75 bar seems a good compromise considering the leakage issue, which intensifies with pressurization (Zarza, 2016). DSG for SHIP at lower than 50 bar pressure is the current practice, due to the smaller size of the facilities and lower temperature required. An additional problem arises in DSG due to the coexistence of liquid and vapor phases in the same horizontal row, with spontaneous large variations of pressure drop owing to the two-phase flow. They can cause not only flow instabilities by themselves but also when interacting with neighbor ones. These issues can result in complicated control and/or the need for pressure reduction valves between rows.

Numerical and experimental studies proved the benefit of pressurization (Muñoz-Anton et al., 2014). They estimated, for a Euro-Trough type 100 m long PTC with CO₂, a pumping power going from 5.24 kW at 25 bar down to 0.53 kW at 75 bar, processing $\dot{m} = 1.1$ kg s⁻¹. Similar values are reported for N₂ under similar conditions. In spite of the pressurization effect, the same ET 100 m PTC would need a lower pumping power of 0.24 kW working with thermal oil (Zarza, 2016). Although pressurization is beneficial, the pressure drops are still a problem when scaling up due to the long piping connecting the loops between them and with the power block. One of the studied solutions is the usage of a molten salt as a secondary fluid carrying heat from the subfield up to the power block, this way keeping the loops at a moderated length of 100 m (Biencinto et al., 2014), or up to 200 m using a larger diameter receiver and larger aperture PTCs, for example, the Iber-Trough type (Biencinto et al., 2019; Figure 5). Bader et al. (2015) estimated the pumping power for an original cavity receiver with a diameter of 450 mm using atmospheric air as HTF. They found a large

variation with \dot{m} , going from 2.5 kW with $\dot{m} \cong 2 \text{ kg s}^{-1}$ up to 47 kW with $\dot{m} \cong 5 \text{ kg s}^{-1}$ on a PTC with a 9 m aperture and 200 m of length.

In SHIP studies, the hydraulic problem is rarely considered explicitly. The original work on an open circuit concentrating solar air heater by Famiglietti et al. (2020) shows that working with air at atmospheric pressure, $\sim 10\%$ of the net solar power gain is needed for pumping using a collector LFC with a 5 m aperture and length of 30 m. It grows to $\sim 20\%$ for a length of 40 m, more than $\sim 50\%$ for a length of 50 m. To overcome the problem, they propose implementing an OAC solar Brayton cycle with null mechanical (power) efficiency aiming to provide heat instead of mechanical power (and/or electricity; Figure 8). It is based on compressing ambient air before solar heating, this way increasing its density for reducing the mean velocity and the stagnation pressure drop. A turbine placed at the receiver outlet expands the airflow down to approximately ambient pressure, releasing a hot air stream at its outlet and providing both the compressing and pumping power. Since no power is extracted at the turbine and compressor common shaft, a standard turbocharger can be used for the duty. As shown in Famiglietti et al. (2021), in a well-designed system, using a compressing ratio from 1.5 to 3.5, typical of turbochargers, and considering the commercial evacuated tube thermal limit, hot airflow at 300–400°C can be provided at the turbine outlet, available for the industrial usage, with no external power consumption for pumping.

3.3 | Thermomechanical issues

The other issue consequent of the low h imposed by a gaseous HTFs is both the increased mechanical stress of the receiver tube and bending, as a consequence of the circumferential temperature gradient.

The concentrated irradiance distribution on the receiver perimeter can be non-homogeneous, resulting from the collector geometry and its optical properties. This is a well-known issue for both PTCs and LFCs (He et al., 2019), even using liquid HTFs. In the case of PTCs, most of the concentrated irradiance heats the receiver tube on its parabola-facing peripheral arc, while the opposite portion of the tube perimeter receives a negligible heat flux. In a typical large PTC for a STE plant, the impacting side of the receiver pipe receives more than 40 kW m^{-2} while the opposite side only receives around 1 kW m^{-2} of nonconcentrated radiation (Figure 9a). The peripheral distribution of heat flux varies with the rim angle, focal length, and collector aperture. Most of the studies use raytracing techniques to simulate the heat flux distribution (He et al., 2019), but also measurements have been also provided (Riffelmann et al., 2006; Schiricke et al., 2009, among others).

LFCs implement more complex optics than PTCs. In principle, the heat flux distribution can be even peakier on the bottom half of the receiver, but the second reflection taking place on the secondary optics increases the sun rays' impact on the upper part of the tube (Figure 9b).

It is worth mentioning that the heat flux is not homogenous along the row length due to non-irradiated segments, which appear due to spacing between consecutive modules or at the extremities of the row due to “optical end losses”

FIGURE 9 Example of heat flux circumferential distribution on the receiver tube: conventional and improved design applying homogenization techniques, including secondary optics. PTC (a) elaborated from He et al. (2019); LFC (b) elaborated from Chaitanya Prasad et al. (2017). LFCs, linear Fresnel collectors; PTCs, parabolic trough collectors.

caused by the longitudinal incidence angle. These increase with de focal length, and its importance is higher in SHIP applications as a result of the smaller L .

The non-uniform heat flux distribution induces a circumferential thermal gradient within the tube wall. The temperature distribution is affected by the internal heat transfer, hence with the flow conditions and the wall heat conduction. Since circumferential temperature gradient drives an axial bending moment originated by differential thermal dilatation of the material, low h for a constant \dot{q}_s leads to increased deformation and mechanical stress, up to plastic deformation risk and loss of focus. Moreover, it can lead to the critical lateral displacement of contact between inner and outer tubes, with the corresponding risk of glass tube rupture and/or coating degradation. This phenomenon is recognized as one of the main causes of failure in PTC-based STEs when a critical flow condition is reached such as low \dot{m} , transient operation, laminar flow, maximum \dot{q}_s (Fuqiang et al., 2017). Operating with gases, that problem is always an issue, even under normal operation, unless adequate secondary optics jointly with a focusing strategy are devised for homogenizing the heat flux.

Several studies deal with the mentioned challenge, although mainly referring to liquid HTFs, using combined numerical simulation techniques (Khanna et al., 2013, 2014, 2015; Marugán-Cruz et al., 2016; Valdés et al., 2014). Still, research is needed to address and quantify the impact of the phenomenon on the large variety of possible applications as well as on the mitigation techniques. Dealing with pressurized gases (Muñoz-Anton et al., 2014) recommended $h \sim 1000 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ to keep maximum circumferential temperature difference in the order of $\sim 50^\circ\text{C}$. Under similar conditions bending was not excessive and cover glass rupture was avoided. The problem is considered in detail for a DSG plant by Roldán et al. (2013), supported by experimental measurements of the thermal gradient on a PTC wall obtained at the DISS facility at PSA (n.d.). Temperature differences up to 45°C were reported in the superheated steam section. A typical value of wall-to-gas h in DSG plants for CSP is $800 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (Zarza, 2016). Famiglietti and Lecuona (2021b) observed tube bending in a small-scale LFC with air as HTF up to 500°C , with lower $h \sim 100 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$. No damage to the evacuated receiver was reported, underlining the beneficial optical diffusion effect of the secondary optics. Besides, a lack of more experimental studies is noticed.

One method of thermal deformation reduction of the tubes through reduction of ΔT_w includes internal heat transfer enhancement. Some studies have been carried out aiming at increasing wall-to-HTF h by installing longitudinal inserts inside the tubular receiver to augment flow turbulence and/or heat transfer surface (M. Shahzad et al., 2021; Sharma & Jilte, 2021). The investigations focus on optimizing the insert features to keep a reasonable excess of friction introduced, either considering wire coils (Yilmaz et al., 2020), a helicoidal screw (Sami, 2021; Song et al., 2014), or a twisted tape (Jaramillo et al., 2016; Mwesigye et al., 2016, among others).

Optical design optimization for more uniform heat flux peripheral distribution is a way for mitigating the problem. A detailed study performed by (Chaitanya Prasad et al., 2017) achieved the homogenization on an LFC for DSG, modifying the shape of the secondary reflector, the location of the focus line, or the curvature of the primary mirrors (Figure 9b). The possibility of adding a secondary reflector in PTC, analogous to the case of LFC, has been investigated to achieve uniform heat flux using different shapes (Figure 9a; Canavarró et al., 2013; He et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Sánchez & Rosengarten, 2015; Wang et al., 2014).

Structural improvement of the receiver tube has been also considered, with the adoption of advanced materials, besides increasing the wall thickness. A compound copper-steel tube has been studied for improving the temperature distribution within the framework of a DSG plant (Almanza et al., 1998; Flores & Almanza, 2004; Khanna et al., 2018). Alternative materials with superior mechanical properties (nickel superalloy or copper) have also been considered (Fuqiang et al., 2017).

4 | CONCLUSIONS

The review of the technical literature, summarized in the previous sections, indicates that relevant research efforts have been devoted to direct gas heating in linear concentrating collectors. The motivations have been explained showing a high potential for improvements. The main issues are presented and analyzed, and the basic steady-state equations are presented so that the interleaving requirements can be fulfilled with a low computing effort. Transient operation is an additional issue that deserves additional research, including the study of failures on some components.

At the same time, a critical analysis suggests that still more work is needed to deeply explore the large variety of technical aspects involved, considering several points of view: theoretical, experimental, economic, environmental, and industrial, for the different applications considered as potential ones.

It is noticed that efforts been made to analyze deeply certain issues, but a systematic and comprehensive assessment has been found still missing. This work is an effort to fill this gap. To complicate the assessment of the solar direct gas heating technology, the applications, as well as the technologies involved, are diverse and some of them still emerging.

The analysis of the literature indicates that the thermal constraints imposed by heat transfer, and the related mechanical aspects such as bending deflection and stresses must be considered together with the hydraulic issues of pressure drop and pumping power. This is of paramount importance for evaluating the viability of a certain fluid as HTF in the herewith case considered of linear concentrating technologies and for determining the optimal design and operating conditions. Although quite a variety of theoretical investigations are available, experimental studies are limited to a few examples.

It is surprising that beyond the authors' publications, there have not been found complementary studies on using pressurized gases for SHIP. A closed loop circuit in SHIP using pressurized air, nitrogen, or carbon dioxide has not been investigated yet but seems promising from the above discussion. Open-to-air circuits concentrating solar energy for air heating is an interesting solution for SHIP for widespread usage of medium-temperature air in industrial processes.

NOMENCLATURE

Latin

A_a	aperture surface area (m^2)
C	solar geometrical concentration factor (—)
c_p	air constant p specific heat capacity ($J\ kg^{-1}\ ^\circ C^{-1}$)
D	inner diameter of the receiver tube (m)
D_h	hydraulic diameter of the receiver tube (m)
f	Darcy friction coefficient (—)
G_{bn}	normal beam irradiance ($W\ m^{-2}$)
h	inner heat transfer coefficient ($W\ m^{-2}\ ^\circ C^{-1}$)
i	specific enthalpy ($J\ kg^{-1}$)
K	concentrated pressure losses coefficient (—)
k	thermal conductivity ($W\ m^{-1}\ ^\circ C^{-1}$)
L	length of the receiver tube (m)
L_c	length of the connection piping (m)
\dot{m}	air mass flow rate [$kg\ s^{-1}$]
P	receiver tube cross-section inner perimeter (m)
Pr	Prandtl number (—)
p	pressure (Pa)
\dot{Q}	thermal power (W)
\dot{q}_s	incident concentrated solar irradiance ($W\ m^{-2}$)
\dot{q}_u	useful thermal power flux ($W\ m^{-2}$)
Re	Reynolds number (—)
T	temperature (K)
U_L	thermal losses overall coefficient ($W\ m^{-2}\ K^{-1}$)
v	average inner flow velocity ($m\ s^{-1}$)
\dot{W}	power (W)
W_a	rectangular aperture total width, aperture (m)
x	axial coordinate

Greek

φ	extension surface coefficient (—)
γ	isentropic exponent (—)
η_{op}	optical efficiency (—)
η_t	thermal efficiency
η_{tt}	total to total isentropic efficiency (—)
μ	dynamic viscosity ($kg\ m^{-1}\ s^{-1}$)
ρ	density ($kg\ m^{-3}$)

Subscripts

amb	ambient
ex	receiver tube external surface
f	friction
in	receiver inlet
k	kinetic
<i>m</i>	average between inlet and outlet
max	maximum
min	minimum
ou	receiver outlet
p	pumping
t	total or stagnation variable

Acronyms

AC	air collector
ETC	evacuated tube collector
HTF	heat transfer fluid
HX	heat exchanger
IAM	incident angle modifier
LFC	linear Fresnel collector
OAC	open-air circuit
PTC	parabolic trough collector
SAH	solar air heater
SHIP	solar heat for industrial processes
STE	solar thermal electricity, according to IEC-62862-1 (Solar Thermal Electricity Plants-Terminology)
T-SAH	turbo-assisted solar air heater

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Antonio Famiglietti: Conceptualization (supporting); data curation (lead); formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); methodology (equal); project administration (supporting); software (lead); validation (equal); visualization (equal); writing – original draft (equal); writing – review and editing (equal). **Antonio Lecuona-Neumann:** Conceptualization (lead); formal analysis (lead); funding acquisition (lead); investigation (lead); methodology (equal); resources (lead); software (supporting); supervision (lead); validation (equal); writing – original draft (equal); writing – review and editing (equal).

FUNDING INFORMATION

The partial funding of the project TURBOSOL, Ref. IND2017/AMB7769 “Producción directa de aire a alta temperatura y a presión turboalimentada en colectores solares de concentración” from the Madrid autonomous government through the research program on doctoral industry is highly appreciated. No additional funding excepting from the Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, has been received.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have declared no conflicts of interest for this article.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study

ORCID

Antonio Lecuona-Neumann <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5763-4982>

Antonio Famiglietti <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0631-345X>

RELATED WIREs ARTICLES

[Thermodynamic cycles for solar thermal power plants: A review](#)
[Solar thermal CSP technology](#)

REFERENCES

- Abbas, R., Montes, M. J., Rovira, A., & Martínez-Val, J. M. (2016). Parabolic trough collector or linear Fresnel collector? A comparison of optical features including thermal quality based on commercial solutions. *Solar Energy*, *124*, 198–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2015.11.039>
- Ahmadi, M. H., Alhuyi Nazari, M., Ghasempour, R., Pourfayaz, F., Rahimzadeh, M., & Ming, T. (2018). A review on solar-assisted gas turbines. *Energy Science and Engineering*, *6*(6), 658–674. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ese3.238>
- Almanza, R., Lentz, A., & Jiménez, G. (1998). Receiver behavior in direct steam generation with parabolic trough. *Solar Energy*, *61*(4), 275–278.
- Amelio, M., Ferraro, V., Marinelli, V., & Summari, A. (2014). An evaluation of the performance of an integrated solar combined cycle plant provided with air-linear parabolic collectors. *Energy*, *69*, 742–748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.03.068>
- Bader, R., Pedretti, A., Barbato, M., & Steinfeld, A. (2015). An air-based corrugated cavity-receiver for solar parabolic trough concentrators. *Applied Energy*, *138*, 337–345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.10.050>
- Behar, O. (2018). Solar thermal power plants—A review of configurations and performance comparison. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *92*(April), 608–627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.04.102>
- Bellos, E. (2019). Progress in the design and the applications of linear Fresnel reflectors—A critical review. *Thermal Science and Engineering Progress*, *10*, 112–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsep.2019.01.014>
- Bellos, E., & Tzivanidis, C. (2017). Parametric investigation of supercritical carbon dioxide utilization in parabolic trough collectors. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, *127*, 736–747. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.08.032>
- Bellos, E., Tzivanidis, C., & Antonopoulos, K. A. (2017a). A detailed working fluid investigation for solar parabolic trough collectors. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, *114*, 374–386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2016.11.201>
- Bellos, E., Tzivanidis, C., & Antonopoulos, K. A. (2017b). Parametric analysis and optimization of a solar assisted gas turbine. *Energy Conversion and Management*, *139*, 151–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.02.042>
- Bellos, E., Tzivanidis, C., Antonopoulos, K. A., & Daniil, I. (2016). The use of gas working fluids in parabolic trough collectors—An energetic and exergetic analysis. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, *109*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2016.08.043>
- Bellos, E., Tzivanidis, C., Daniil, I., & Antonopoulos, K. A. (2017). The impact of internal longitudinal fins in parabolic trough collectors operating with gases. *Energy Conversion and Management*, *135*, 35–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2016.12.057>
- Benoit, H., Spreafico, L., Gauthier, D., & Flamant, G. (2016). Review of heat transfer fluids in tube-receivers used in concentrating solar thermal systems: Properties and heat transfer coefficients. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *55*, 298–315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.10.059>
- Bernhard, R., Laabs, H., & Lalaing, J. D. (2008). Linear Fresnel collector demonstration on the PSA, part I—Design, construction and quality control. *SolarPaces*, 1–10. http://www.researchgate.net/publication/225000351_Linear_Fresnel_Collector_Demonstration_on_the_PSA_Part_I_Design_Construction_and_Quality_Control/file/60b7d515e950a285ce.pdf
- Biencinto, M., González, L., Valenzuela, L., & Zarza, E. (2019). A new concept of solar thermal power plants with large-aperture parabolic-trough collectors and sCO₂ as working fluid. *Energy Conversion and Management*, *199*, 112030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.112030>
- Biencinto, M., González, L., Zarza, E., Díez, L. E., & Muñoz-Antón, J. (2014). Performance model and annual yield comparison of parabolic-trough solar thermal power plants with either nitrogen or synthetic oil as heat transfer fluid. *Energy Conversion and Management*, *87*, 238–249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2014.07.017>
- Bilal Awan, A., Khan, M. N., Zubair, M., & Bellos, E. (2020). Commercial parabolic trough CSP plants: Research trends and technological advancements. *Solar Energy*, *211*(September), 1422–1458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2020.09.072>
- Burkholder, F., & Kutscher, C. F. (2009). Heat loss testing of Schott's 2008 PTR70 parabolic trough receiver. *NREL Technical Report*, May, p. 58. <http://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy09osti/45633.pdf>
- Canavarró, D., Chaves, J., & Collares-Pereira, M. (2013). New second-stage concentrators (XX SMS) for parabolic primaries; comparison with conventional parabolic trough concentrators. *Solar Energy*, *92*, 98–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2013.02.011>
- Chaitanya Prasad, G. S., Reddy, K. S., & Sundararajan, T. (2017). Optimization of solar linear Fresnel reflector system with secondary concentrator for uniform flux distribution over absorber tube. *Solar Energy*, *150*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.04.026>
- Cheng, W. L., Huang, W. X., & Nian, Y. L. (2017). Global parameter optimization and criterion formula of supercritical carbon dioxide Brayton cycle with recompression. *Energy Conversion and Management*, *150*, 669–677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.08.055>
- Cheng, Z. D., Men, J. J., Zhao, X. R., He, Y. L., & Tao, Y. B. (2019). A comprehensive study on parabolic trough solar receiver-reactors of methanol-steam reforming reaction for hydrogen production. *Energy Conversion and Management*, *186*, 278–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.02.068>
- Cinocca, A., Cipollone, R., Carapellucci, R., Iampieri, V., & Rivo, M. (2018). CSP-PT gas plant using air as heat transfer fluid with a packed-bed storage section. *73rd Conference of the Italian Thermal Machines Engineering Association (ATI 2018)*, 12–14 September 2018, Pisa, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2018.08.110>
- Crespi, F., Sánchez, D., Rodríguez, J. M., & Gavagnin, G. (2020). A thermo-economic methodology to select sCO₂ power cycles for CSP applications. *Renewable Energy*, *147*, 2905–2912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.08.023>
- Cundapí, R., Moya, S. L., & Valenzuela, L. (2017). Approaches to modelling a solar field for direct generation of industrial steam. *Renewable Energy*, *103*, 666–681. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2016.10.081>

- Dabwan, Y. N., Pei, G., Hu, T., Zhang, H., & Zhao, B. (2022). Development and assessment of a low-emissions gas turbine system for power utilities incorporating intercooling and solar preheating. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 218, 119335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2022.119335>
- Duffie, J. A., Beckman, W. A., & McGowan, J. (1985). Solar engineering of thermal processes. *American Journal of Physics*, 53(4). <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.14178>
- Eck, M., Hirsch, T., Feldhoff, J. F., Kretschmann, D., Dersch, J., Gavilan Morales, A., Gonzalez-Martinez, L., Bachelier, C., Platzer, W., Riffelmann, K. J., & Wagner, M. (2014). Guidelines for CSP yield analysis—Optical losses of line focusing systems; definitions, sensitivity analysis and modeling approaches. *Energy Procedia*, 49, 1318–1327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.03.141>
- Eck, M., Zarza, E., Eickhoff, M., Rheinländer, J., & Valenzuela, L. (2003). Applied research concerning the direct steam generation in parabolic troughs. *Solar Energy*, 74(4), 341–351. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-092X\(03\)00111-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-092X(03)00111-7)
- Famiglietti, A., & Lecuona, A. (2021a). Direct solar air heating inside small-scale linear Fresnel collector assisted by a turbocharger: Experimental characterization. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 196, 117323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2021.117323>
- Famiglietti, A., & Lecuona, A. (2021b). Small-scale linear Fresnel collector using air as heat transfer fluid: Experimental characterization. *Renewable Energy*, 176, 459–474.
- Famiglietti, A., Lecuona, A., Ibarra, M., & Roa, J. (2021). Turbo-assisted direct solar air heater for medium temperature industrial processes using linear Fresnel collectors. Assessment on daily and yearly basis. *Energy*, 223, 120011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.120011>
- Famiglietti, A., Lecuona-Neumann, A., Nogueira, J., & Rahjoo, M. (2020). Direct solar production of medium temperature hot air for industrial applications in linear concentrating solar collectors using an open Brayton cycle. Viability analysis. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 169, 114914. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2020.114914>
- Farjana, S. H., Huda, N., Mahmud, M. A. P., & Saidur, R. (2018). Solar process heat in industrial systems—A global review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82, 2270–2286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.08.065>
- Ferraro, V., & Marinelli, V. (2012). An evaluation of thermodynamic solar plants with cylindrical parabolic collectors and air turbine engines with open Joule–Brayton cycle. *Energy*, 44(1), 862–869. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2012.05.005>
- Flores, V., & Almanza, R. (2004). Behavior of the compound wall copper—Steel receiver with stratified two-phase flow regimen in transient states when solar irradiance is arriving on one side of receiver, 76, 195–198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2003.08.015>
- Forristall, R. (2003). Heat transfer analysis and modeling of a parabolic trough solar receiver implemented in engineering equation solver. *Energy Procedia*, 57, 401–410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.10.193>
- Fuqiang, W., Ziming, C., Jianyu, T., Yuan, Y., Yong, S., & Linhua, L. (2017). Progress in concentrated solar power technology with parabolic trough collector system: A comprehensive review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 79(May), 1314–1328. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.174>
- Gharat, P. V., Bhalekar, S. S., Dalvi, V. H., Panse, S. V., Deshmukh, S. P., & Joshi, J. B. (2021). Chronological development of innovations in reflector systems of parabolic trough solar collector (PTC)—A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 145, 111002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111002>
- Giglio, A., Lanzini, A., Leone, P., Rodríguez García, M. M., & Zarza Moya, E. (2017). Direct steam generation in parabolic-trough collectors: A review about the technology and a thermo-economic analysis of a hybrid system. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 74, 453–473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.176>
- Giostrì, A., Binotti, M., Silva, P., Macchi, E., & Manzolini, G. (2011). Comparison of two linear collectors in solar thermal plants: Parabolic trough vs Fresnel. *Proceedings of the ASME 2011 International Conference on Energy Sustainability*.
- Good, P., Ambrosetti, G., Pedretti, A., & Steinfeld, A. (2015). An array of coiled absorber tubes for solar trough concentrators operating with air at 600°C and above. *Solar Energy*, 111, 378–395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2014.09.016>
- Haagen, M., Zahler, C., Zimmermann, E., & Al-Najami, M. M. R. (2015). Solar process steam for pharmaceutical industry in Jordan. *Energy Procedia*, 70, 621–625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2015.02.169>
- He, Y. L., Wang, K., Qiu, Y., Du, B. C., Liang, Q., & Du, S. (2019). Review of the solar flux distribution in concentrated solar power: Non-uniform features, challenges, and solutions. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 149, 448–474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2018.12.006>
- Holler, S., Winkelmann, A., Pelda, J., & Salaymeh, A. (2021). Feasibility study on solar thermal process heat in the beverage industry. *Energy*, 233, 121153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121153>
- Hongn, M., & Flores Larsen, S. (2018). Hydrothermal model for small-scale linear Fresnel absorbers with non-uniform stepwise solar distribution. *Applied Energy*, 223, 329–346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.04.056>
- Incropera, F. P., & DeWitt, D. P. (1996). *Fundamentals of heat and mass transfer* (p. 890). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- International Energy Agency. (2018). *Key World Energy Statistics 2019*. International Energy Agency IEA. <https://www.iea.org/events/key-world-energy-statistics-2019>
- International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). (n.d.). www.irena.org
- Inventive Power (n.d.). <https://inventivepower.com.mx/solucion-en-energia-solar/>
- Jaramillo, O. A., Borunda, M., Velazquez-Lucho, K. M., & Robles, M. (2016). Parabolic trough solar collector for low enthalpy processes: An analysis of the efficiency enhancement by using twisted tape inserts. *Renewable Energy*, 93, 125–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2016.02.046>
- Karathanasis, S. (2019). Linear Fresnel reflector systems for solar radiation concentration. In *Linear Fresnel reflector systems for solar radiation concentration*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-05279-9>

- Kasperski, J., & Nemš, M. (2013). Investigation of thermo-hydraulic performance of concentrated solar air-heater with internal multiple-fin array. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 58(1–2), 411–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2013.04.018>
- Khanna, S., Kedare, S. B., & Singh, S. (2013). Analytical expression for circumferential and axial distribution of absorbed flux on a bent absorber tube of solar parabolic trough concentrator. *Solar Energy*, 92, 26–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2013.02.020>
- Khanna, S., Kedare, S. B., & Singh, S. (2014). Deflection and stresses in absorber tube of solar parabolic trough due to circumferential and axial flux variations on absorber tube supported at multiple points. *Solar Energy*, 99, 134–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2013.11.005>
- Khanna, S., Newar, S., Sharma, V., Panigrahi, P. K., & Mallick, T. K. (2018). Deformation of receiver in solar parabolic trough collector due to non-uniform temperature and solar flux distribution and use of bimetallic absorber tube with multiple supports. *Energy*, 165, 1078–1088. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.09.145>
- Khanna, S., Singh, S., & Kedare, S. B. (2015). Explicit expressions for temperature distribution and deflection in absorber tube of solar parabolic trough concentrator. *Solar Energy*, 114, 289–302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2015.01.044>
- Lecuona-Neumann, A. (2016). *Secadero solar* (Patent No. P201630068).
- Loni, R., Mahian, O., Markides, C. N., Bellos, E., le Roux, W. G., Kasaeian, A., Najafi, G., & Rajaei, F. (2021). A review of solar-driven organic Rankine cycles: Recent challenges and future outlook. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 150, 111410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111410>
- Ma, Z., & Turchi, C. S. (2011). Advanced supercritical carbon dioxide power cycle configurations for use in concentrating solar power systems: Preprint. Presented at the *Supercritical CO₂ Power Cycle Symposium*, 24–25 May 2011, Boulder, Colorado, March. <https://digital.library.unt.edu/ark:/67531/metadc833207/>
- Marugán-Cruz, C., Flores, O., Santana, D., & García-Villalba, M. (2016). Heat transfer and thermal stresses in a circular tube with a non-uniform heat flux. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 96, 256–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2016.01.035>
- Mekhilef, S., Saidur, R., & Safari, A. (2011). A review on solar energy use in industries. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 15(4), 1777–1790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2010.12.018>
- Montes, M. J., Barbero, R., Abbas, R., & Rovira, A. (2016). Performance model and thermal comparison of different alternatives for the Fresnel single-tube receiver. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 104, 162–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2016.05.015>
- Montes, M. J., Rubbia, C., Abbas, R., & Martínez-Val, J. M. (2014). A comparative analysis of configurations of linear Fresnel collectors for concentrating solar power. *Energy*, 73, 192–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.06.010>
- Morin, G., Dersch, J., Platzer, W., Eck, M., & Häberle, A. (2012). Comparison of linear Fresnel and parabolic trough collector power plants. *Solar Energy*, 86(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2011.06.020>
- Muñoz-Anton, J., Biencinto, M., Zarza, E., & Díez, L. E. (2014). Theoretical basis and experimental facility for parabolic trough collectors at high temperature using gas as heat transfer fluid. *Applied Energy*, 135, 373–381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.08.099>
- Mwesigye, A., Bello-ochende, T., & Meyer, J. P. (2016). Heat transfer and entropy generation in a parabolic trough receiver with wall-detached twisted tape inserts. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 99, 238–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijthermalsci.2015.08.015>
- Pietruschka, D., Hassine, I. B., Cotrado, M., Fedrizzi, R., & Cozzini, M. (2016). Large scale solar process heat systems -planning, realization and system operation. *Energy Procedia*, 91, 638–649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2016.06.223>
- Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA). (n.d.). www.psa.es
- Rehman, S., Ahmad, A., Alhems, L. M., & Rafique, M. M. (2019). Experimental evaluation of solar thermal performance of linear Fresnel reflector. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*, 33(9), 4555–4562. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12206-019-0852-6>
- Riffelmann, K. J., Neumann, A., & Ulmer, S. (2006). Performance enhancement of parabolic trough collectors by solar flux measurement in the focal region. *Solar Energy*, 80(10), 1303–1313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2005.09.001>
- Rioglass. (n.d.). <https://www.rioglass.com/>
- Rodríguez-Sánchez, D., & Rosengarten, G. (2015). Improving the concentration ratio of parabolic troughs using a second-stage flat mirror. *Applied Energy*, 159, 620–632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.08.106>
- Roldán, M. I., Valenzuela, L., & Zarza, E. (2013). Thermal analysis of solar receiver pipes with superheated steam. *Applied Energy*, 103, 73–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2012.10.021>
- Salcedo-Abraira, P., Vilela, S. M. F., Babaryk, A. A., Cabrero-Antonino, M., Gregorio, P., Salles, F., Navalón, S., García, H., & Horcajada, P. (2021). Nickel phosphonate MOF as efficient water splitting photocatalyst. *Nano Research*, 14(2), 450–457. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-020-3056-6>
- Sami, M. (2021). Experimental performance analysis of a parabolic trough solar air collector with helical-screw tape insert: A comparative study. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 47, 101562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101562>
- Sarkar, J. (2015). Review and future trends of supercritical CO₂ Rankine cycle for low-grade heat conversion. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 48, 434–451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.04.039>
- Saxena, A., Varun, G., & El-Sebaei, A. A. (2015). A thermodynamic review of solar air heaters. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 43, 863–890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.11.059>
- Schiricke, B., Pitz-Paal, R., Lüpfer, E., Pottler, K., Pfänder, M., Riffelmann, K. J., & Neumann, A. (2009). Experimental verification of optical modeling of parabolic trough collectors by flux measurement. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering, Transactions of the ASME*, 131(1), 011004. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3027507>
- Sepúlveda, F. J., Miranda, M. T., Montero, I., Arranz, J. I., Lozano, F. J., Matamoros, M., & Rodríguez, P. (2019). Analysis of potential use of linear Fresnel collector for direct steam generation in industries of the southwest of Europe. *Energies*, 12(21), 4049. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12214049>

- Shahzad, M., Shahsavar, A., Afrand, M., Arıcı, M., & Ni, S. (2021). A comprehensive review of parabolic trough solar collectors equipped with turbulators and numerical evaluation of hydrothermal performance of a novel model. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 45, 101103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101103>
- Sharma, A. K., Sharma, C., Mullick, S. C., & Kandpal, T. C. (2017). Solar industrial process heating: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 78, 124–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.04.079>
- Sharma, M., & Jilte, R. (2021). A review on passive methods for thermal performance enhancement in parabolic trough solar collectors. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 45(4), 4932–4966. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.6212>
- SHIP Database (n.d.). <http://ship-plants.info/>
- Solatom. (n.d.). Solar steam for industrial processes. <http://www.solatom.com/>
- Song, X., Dong, G., Gao, F., Diao, X., & Zheng, L. (2014). A numerical study of parabolic trough receiver with nonuniform heat flux and helical screw-tape inserts. *Energy*, 77, 771–782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.09.049>
- Valdés, A., Almanza, R., & Soria, A. (2014). Determining the deflection magnitude of a steel receiver from a DSG parabolic trough concentrator under stratified flow conditions. *Energy Procedia*, 57, 341–350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.10.039>
- Wang, K., He, Y., & Cheng, Z. (2014). A design method and numerical study for a new type parabolic trough solar collector with uniform solar flux distribution. *Science China Technological Sciences*, 57(3), 531–540. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11431-013-5452-6>
- Warren, K. J., & Weimer, A. W. (2022). Solar thermochemical fuels: Present status and future prospects. *Solar Compass*, 1(April), 100010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solcom.2022.100010>
- Xu, G., Song, G., Zhu, X., Gao, W., Li, H., & Quan, Y. (2015). Performance evaluation of a direct vapor generation supercritical ORC system driven by linear Fresnel reflector solar concentrator. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 80, 196–204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2014.12.071>
- Xuening, F., Lei, C., Yuman, D., Min, J., & Jinping, F. (2015). CFD modeling and analysis of brine spray evaporation system integrated with solar collector. *Desalination*, 366, 139–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2015.02.027>
- Yılmaz, İ. H., Mwesigye, A., & Göksu, T. T. (2020). Enhancing the overall thermal performance of a large aperture parabolic trough solar collector using wire coil inserts. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 39, 100696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2020.100696>
- Zarza, E., Rojas, M. E., González, L., Caballero, J. M., & Rueda, F. (2006). INDITEP: The first pre-commercial DSG solar power plant. *Solar Energy*, 80(10), 1270–1276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2005.04.019>
- Zarza, E. M. (2016). Innovative working fluids for parabolic trough collectors. In *Advances in concentrating solar thermal research and technology*. Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100516-3.00005-8>
- Zhu, G., Wendelin, T., Wagner, M. J., & Kutscher, C. (2014). History, current state, and future of linear Fresnel concentrating solar collectors. *Solar Energy*, 103, 639–652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2013.05.021>

How to cite this article: Lecuona-Neumann, A., & Famiglietti, A. (2023). Direct gas heating in linear concentrating solar collectors for power and industrial process heat production: Applications and challenges. *WIREs Energy and Environment*, 12(4), e471. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.471>